

Thus with these ratios it can be concluded that tinperoxychromate contains $(Cr_2O_{10})^{-2}$ ion in its constitution.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Dr. M. Behari, S. V. College Aligarh and Dr. D. R. Singh, R. B. S. College, Agra for their help.

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Some Dyes as Visual Indicators for Titration of Organic Acids in Alcohol Medium

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Manuscript received 21 November 1975, accepted 18 February 1976

TITRATION in alcohol is extensively used in varnish, oil and many other chemical industries for determination of acid value. Generally, phenolphthalein is used as the indicator; it is however far from satisfactory, the colour change being faint and unsharp much unlike that in water medium. Some indicators specially of sulphonaphthalein class have been recommended¹, though hardly ever used. Palit² was the earliest to introduce thymol blue (whose pK is rather unfavourable for normal aqueous titration) in non-aqueous titration; however, its sensitivity is strongly affected by the presence of small quantities of water. In this note we draw attention to the possibility of using some ordinary dyes as indicators which normally do not function as acid-base indicators in aqueous medium.

Experimental

During our studies of electrolysis of dyes in W-tubes in alcoholic solution to produce multiple boundaries³ we noted that quite a few dyes form contrasting colours between the cathodic solution (alkaline) and the anodic solution (acidic), though they do not normally behave as acid-base indicators in water. This is not at all surprising as red form of methylene blue is well-known⁴. Our results for titration of a number of weak organic acids using some such dyes, which are found satisfactory are briefly summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Dyes and indicators	Colour change acid - alkali	Sharpness of colour change in absolute alcohol	
		N/10 acid	N/100 acid
Aniline blue	Red to blue	Extremely sharp	Good
Victoria blue	—do—	—do—	Good
Thionine blue	—do—	Very sharp	Fair
Methylene blue	—do—	Fair	Poor
Thymol blue	Yellow to blue	Extremely sharp	Good

A number of blue dyes whose basic form is red has been found to serve as excellent indicators. Aniline blue and victoria blue are strongly recommended for such titration. The change of colour is very sharp and occurs at the theoretical point. There is no 'blank' and neutral rectified spirit can also be used. For very precise results the titration should be done with exclusion of CO₂, as CO₂ tends to change the red form to blue. The commercial dyes can be used as such. For very precise work the dye should be used after conversion to the red form which can be obtained at the anode on electrolysis of the dye solution in a W-tube^{2,3} (the dye solution in alcohol being charged into the cathode chamber only, the rest being filled with alcohol). Commercial alcohol-soluble resins (such as resin, pale shellac, etc.) and oils, unless too dark, can be successfully titrated with precision.

Thymol blue is almost as good as the dyes mentioned above but tends to give slightly low results. Also, as mentioned earlier, its sensitivity decreases very much in presence of water and so is somewhat unsatisfactory in rectified spirit. Methylene blue is not quite as satisfactory as the aforementioned dyes; however its sensitivity increases if used in its 'red' form obtained either by electrolysis or by benzene extraction⁵.

It is hoped that these dyes should be used in routine industrial determination of acid value of commercial products.

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A Dye as a Catalyst for Decomposition of Hydrogen Peroxide

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Manuscript received 21 November 1975; accepted 18 February 1976

THERE has lately been great revival of interest in the study of the rate of catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂ due to its evident relevance to enzyme action. In particular many metal-organic compounds have been

recently receiving attention as catalyst¹⁻⁵. In this preliminary note we report the catalytic power of the dye, Rose Bengale.

Results and Discussion

To screen the dyes for catalytic power we measured the rate of oxygen evolution from a hydrogen peroxide solution with and without addition of the dye. Particular attention was paid that the final solutions were below pH 7 at which the rate of H₂O₂ decomposition is practically nil near room temperature. From spectrophotometric measurements it has been checked that the dye undergoes very little oxidation and the same dye is effective over many cycles of catalytic operations. From these experiments it has been found that among the dyes tried (listed below) only Rose Bengale and Erythrosin have fairly good catalytic power. It is to be noted that though Eosin and Iodo-eosin, are structurally similar to Rose Bengale yet their catalytic power in this decomposition reaction is nil and very little respectively.

List of dyes tested in the preliminary experiment

(1) Direct Sky Blue, (2) Azo carmine GX, (3) Rose Bengale, (4) Direct Brown, (5) Anthosin violet, (6) Biebrich Scarlet, (7) Direct Green B, (8) Chlorantine, (9) Chlorantine Fast Yellow (10) Tropaeolin O, (11) Eosin, (12) Iodo-eosin and (13) Erythrosin.

To have a clear idea of the catalytic power of Rose Bengale, this dye-catalysed decomposition of H₂O₂ was run at three different temperatures. The extent of reaction was measured by the volume of oxygen liberated in the gas burette attached to the reaction vessel. A control experiment (without adding the dye) was run side by side. The value of the rate constant (K_1) was determined from the slope of the plot of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs. time where V_∞ and V_t are respectively the initial total volume of oxygen in the H₂O₂ solution and that liberated after the interval of a certain time t . Energy of activation of the reaction was determined from the slope of the plot of $\log k_1$ vs. $1/T$ where T = temperature. Just to have an idea of the comparative efficiency of Rose Bengale we performed the same set of experiments using the conventional catalyst KI, whose results are included in the Table. The iodide ion is found to be about five times more efficient in equimolar concentration and to have somewhat lower energy of activation.

Mechanism. Most mechanisms of catalytic H₂O₂ decomposition involves an electron transfer mechanism involving oxidation-reduction cycles of the catalyst. Here such a mechanism is not possible because this dye is known to be irreversibly oxidised. This dye like most dyes of this group is devoid of colloidal properties. So we prefer the concept of a complex formation between the dye molecule and the H₂O₂. This intermediate is assumed to be rather unstable; the H₂O₂ moiety probably being under strain decomposes monomolecularly and the dye molecule undergoes such process again and again. However, we could not get any spectrophotometric evidence for the complex formation except that the shoulder at 517 nm tends to disappear

in presence of H₂O₂ leaving the main absorption peak (550 nm) almost unaffected.

TABLE 1

Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ (M)	Conc. of Catalyst (M)	Temp. °C	K ₁ (Dye) × 10 ⁶	K ₁ (Iodide) × 10 ⁶	E (Dye) KCal/mole	E (Iodide) KCal/mole
		32.5	4.55	2.43(32°C)		
2	3 × 10 ⁻⁴	38	7.52	3.18	13.14	11.5
		42	9.19	3.49		

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Reductive Dimerisation of Flavonoids : Syntheses of Some Biflavonoids

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Manuscript received 30 September 1975, revised 7 January 1976, accepted 18 February 1976

METAL reduction reactions have been used since long to characterise flavonoids and various explanations have been offered for the coloured products formed in these reactions¹⁻⁶. Biflavenylidenes were found in the reductive acetylation⁷ products of flavonoids, contrary to the formation of only monomeric products as reported earlier. Jurd⁴ isolated crystalline biflavenylidenes, concluding thereby that the flavones unsubstituted in the 3 and 5 positions form dimeric bisflavenylidenes under the conditions of reductive acetylation. Russel and Clark⁸ showed that the reduction of chalcones by zinc dust and alcoholic acid produced compounds which were qualitatively indistinguishable from the natural phlobatannins and flavpinacols. These reductive reactions usually yield complicated mixtures from which pure reduction products have rarely been separated and characterised.

During the present work 6,2'; 6,3' and 6,4'-dihydroxy flavanones were synthesised by acid cyclisation of the corresponding chalcones, which in turn were prepared by the condensation of the corresponding acetophenone derivatives and substituted benzaldehydes. On treatment with sodium amalgam in alcohol and subsequent acidification, these flavanones underwent reductive dimerisation yielding the corresponding biflavonoids [I (a), (b) and (c)], which could be isolated in the pure form from the reaction mixtures.